

HABITABLE

HABITABLE Project Synthesis Report

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The **HABITABLE** project – Linking Climate Change, Habitability and Social Tipping Points: Scenarios for Climate Migration – aims at significantly advance our understanding of the **current interlinkages between climate change impacts and migration** and displacement patterns, and to **better anticipate their future evolution**.

Running for **4 years** (2020-2024), HABITABLE brings together **21 partners**: University of Liège, University of Vienna, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), University of Exeter, the IDMC, Lund University, Sapienza Università di Roma, adelphi, Université de Neuchâtel, Institut de Recherche pour le Développement, Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, UNESCO, University of Ghana, CARE France, University of Twente, Université Cheikh Anta Diop, Stockholm Environment Institute Asia, Raks Thai Foundation, Addis Ababa University, Institut National de la Statistique du Mali and Samuel Hall.

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Abstract

The project **HABITABLE – Linking Climate Change, Habitability and Social Tipping Points: Scenarios for Climate Migration** – aimed to significantly advance our understanding of the interlinkages between climate change impacts and migration and displacement patterns, and to better anticipate their future evolution. Bringing together 22 partners from 18 countries, HABITABLE (2020–2024) serves as a reference project in climate-mobility research.

This project synthesis report has two core aims: (1) to summarise the **practical, conceptual, and methodological contributions** of HABITABLE to the field of research; and (2) to describe a number of intersecting and complementary **novel findings** generated by the project, made possible through the **triangulation of diverse methods and methodological innovations** that advance research on the climate–migration nexus. These include quantitative surveys, Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping (FCM), qualitative interviews, focus group discussions (FGDs), and quantitative modelling.

The project made significant advances over previous efforts in the field through several **methodological and practical innovations**, including: the co-development of research and policy solutions with local researchers and stakeholders through scenario narratives and planning, validated by community participants; the effective use of remote and online coordination tools, which strengthened North–South knowledge exchange during Covid-19; and the systematic integration of gender and social equity across all stages of research, enabling a robust intersectional analysis.

The “**Novel Findings**” section of this report echoes the four key objectives of the project. First, we develop understandings of migration trends by **identifying tipping points** at which environmental and social conditions render areas “inhabitable.” Second, we assess **how migration reshapes adaptation limits**, in order to explore context-specific strategies used by affected populations. Third, **gender and social equity considerations** are embedded in the project’s theoretical framework, data collection processes, analysis, and policy engagement. Lastly, we offer **policy recommendations** to improve the governance of climate-induced migration and reduce displacement risks, while fostering better integration of climate and migration policies globally.

We include annexes with an extended project bibliography, additional research findings identified in the project, and information about the HABITABLE final conference objectives and agenda.

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Executive Summary

“HABITABLE – Linking Climate Change, Habitability and Social Tipping Points: Scenarios for Climate Migration” aimed at significantly advance our understanding of the current interlinkages between climate impacts and migration and displacement patterns, and to better anticipate their future evolution. Bringing together 22 partners from 18 countries, HABITABLE (2020-2024) serves as a reference project in climate-mobility research.

The HABITABLE project pursued four key objectives to address climate-related migration. First, it develops understandings of migration trends by identifying tipping points where environmental and social conditions render areas “inhabitable”. Second, it assesses how migration reshapes adaptation limits to explore context-specific strategies of affected populations. Third, it integrates gender and social equity considerations throughout the project’s theoretical framework, data processes, and policy engagement. Lastly, HABITABLE offers policy recommendations to improve the governance of climate-induced migration and reduce displacement risks, while fostering better integration of climate and migration policies globally.

The HABITABLE project made significant improvements over previous generations of projects on the climate-migration nexus through several methodological and practical innovations, including: co-development of research and policy solutions with local researchers and stakeholders, validated by community participants; the effective use of remote and online coordination tools, which strengthened North-South knowledge exchange; and the systematic integration of gender and social equity across all stages of research, enabling a robust intersectional analysis.

The scientific strength of the HABITABLE project lies in its triangulation of diverse methods and its methodological innovations that advance research on the climate-migration nexus through a number of intersecting and complementary **novel findings**:¹

Across Sub-Saharan Africa, an increase of out-migration is being driven by climate-related social tipping points, with temperature anomalies playing a key role, according to results from regression discontinuity analysis of HABITABLE survey; an increase of one standard deviation in temperature anomalies raises out-migration rates by 5.2 percentage points in Ghana and 6.3 in Ethiopia, with nonlinear jumps in migration rates occurring at approximately 0.5°C and 0.4°C above the long-term mean, respectively (Gavonel et al., in prep). This finding is supported by fixed-effects statistical analyses of LSMS-ISA survey data in Eastern Africa, which show that **environmental and climatic shocks have a compounding effect on livelihoods**, as they are associated with increased out-migration probabilities across multiple time periods following the shock (Blocher et al., 2024). Migration takes time to prepare, and **some households may only migrate after the impacts of adverse events become clearer** or more severe.

¹ Presented in the order they appear in the main text below. Additional findings are in Annex 2.

Perceptions of changing risks by those experiencing them is central to migration decision-making in response, as individuals continuously reassess and renegotiate their circumstances, capabilities, and aspirations once migration begins as well as over their lifetimes – and analysis of new Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping (FCM) networks identifies context-specific webs of causalities (Reckien et al., 2025). Migration becomes a more acceptable or effective response over time, as **many individuals from migrant households perceive it as an effective strategy in hindsight, even if it was not a chosen immediate response** to past events (D. A. Serraglio & Blocher, 2025; D. Serraglio & Blocher, 2025; Sterly et al., 2025).

Novel negative binomial regression analysis shows that **migration is synergistic with adaptive capacities**, increasing uptake of other in-situ adaptation measures (Redicker et al., in prep). Therefore, migration is not opposed to other adaptation strategies. Qualitatively, **however, enhanced adaptive capacities do not necessarily translate into proactive adaptive action** for certain people who have little perceived capacity, or hope, to prepare response strategies (D. A. Serraglio & Blocher, 2025).

Gender-focused analysis shows that the uneven distribution of adaptive capacity within households and communities notably affects adaptation portfolios to respond to adverse climate conditions and events, including migration decisions (Redicker et al., in prep). In particular, **adaptive capacity is gendered and significantly influences household adaptation** to climate shocks. Moreover, targeted qualitative research in Southeast Asia reveals how **climate stressors increase vulnerabilities to labour exploitation and trafficking**, particularly among male heads of households, challenging traditional gendered narratives (Betancourt, in prep). More research on the climate change-migration-gender nexus is needed (Betancourt & Zickgraf, 2024).

Novel global scenario simulations demonstrate that **under a 3°C warming scenario, climate-driven economic impacts may shift international migration flows by about 1%** (Rikani et al., 2022). The study explores different scenarios for how climate change impacts macroeconomic development, examining two mechanisms for international migration: (1) destination-country income is positively related to immigration, and (2) origin-country income has an inverse U-shaped relationship with emigration (the “migration hump”). The investigation shows that **climate change, by slowing down economic development especially in the Global South, delays countries’ transition across the hypothesized inverse U-shaped relationship**. This means countries that are today relatively poor are projected to experience high emigration rates for a longer time than without climate change. The study highlights that uneven economic changes across countries shape mobility patterns, and that simple net migration figures obscure important underlying dynamics. This research adds to growing evidence that **climate change affects not only internal but also long-term international migration**. Until now, climate change

has likely inhibited global migration through macroeconomic effects in both high- and low-income countries (Rikani et al., 2023).

Widely-used quantitative migration models, particularly **gravity models, have demonstrated their significant disadvantages and mathematical shortcomings**, according to the most significant critique to-date of these approaches (Beyer et al., 2022, 2023). Other quantitative approaches can however improve certain projections, such as a **new stochastic model for country-to-country migration** that hindcasted simulations matching bilateral migrant stock data across world regions and income groups (Zantout & Schewe, 2024). Moreover, novel probabilistic modelling approaches considering different scenarios can elucidate possible risk scenarios, suggesting **climate change may cause flood-related displacement risk to increase by two to four times** compared with current conditions (Zimmermann et al., in rev.).

Most legal and policy provisions to address the climate-mobility nexus are recent, unspecific, and fail to address vulnerability conditions driving migration, according to the most comprehensive global analysis to date of 700 documents, including case law, UN resolutions, and regional advisory opinions highlighting state obligations to support vulnerable populations (Marchisio et al., 2024), complemented by an examination of over 100 national legal and policy instruments across six HABITABLE study countries and their regional frameworks (D. A. Serraglio & Blocher, in prep).

Co-developed novel scenarios exploring potential futures reveal both **site-specific entry points for political action and common themes** across all scenarios – in particular, **the need for investment in adaptation and livelihood diversification to sustain habitability as well as the central importance of public goods**, such as basic services, social safety nets and insurance, in strengthening habitability and resilience across the board (adelphi, 2024; Wright-O'Kelly et al., 2024).

Part 1: HABITABLE Objectives, Methods, and Contributions to the Field

1.1. Objectives

“HABITABLE – Linking Climate Change, Habitability and Social Tipping Points: Scenarios for Climate Migration” aimed at significantly advance our understanding of the current interlinkages between climate impacts and migration and displacement patterns, and to better anticipate their future evolution. Bringing together 22 partners from 18 countries, HABITABLE (2020-2024) was, to date, the largest research project on climate change and migration to have ever been funded by the European Commission’s Horizon 2020 programme. The consortium’s research centred around notions of habitability and aimed to formulate a broader and interdisciplinary conceptualisation of social tipping points, thresholds at which environmental disruptions can potentially trigger major social changes like out-migration.

HABITABLE consisted of three intersecting and research domains: 1) Web of Casualties, 2) Adaptation, and 3) Policies, which are complemented by two transversal components: Gender and social equity, and Stakeholder engagement. Intentionally steering away from simple linear assumptions, HABITABLE adopts a systems-based approach accounting for the interactions between climate impacts and other drivers of human mobility – including social, political, economic, environmental and demographic factors. HABITABLE’s systemic approach also contributes to the design of appropriate and sustainable policy responses to the climate-mobility nexus (see §1.5, page 15, and §2.4, page 35).

The ambitions of HABITABLE are achieved through four overarching objectives:

- **Key Objective 1 (KO1):** Develop a predictive understanding of migration trends under climate change, by identifying social tipping points at which socio-ecological systems breakdown and are no longer perceived to be inhabitable, leading to migration.
- **Key Objective 2 (KO2):** Propose adaptation options [solutions] and strategies for populations affected by climate change based on an assessment of how migration redefines the limits to adaptation in different contexts.
- **Key Objective 3 (KO3):** HABITABLE shall identify, analyse and mainstream the gendered and social equity dimensions of the climate-migration nexus in terms of theoretical framing, data collection, data analysis, as well as research dissemination and policy engagement in key components of the project.
- **Key Objective 4 (KO4):** Develop guidelines and recommendations to allow policies to better address the migration patterns associated with climate change, with the goal to improve the management of migration movements induced by climate change and with the aim of reducing the risk of displacement. These recommendations will adopt a European perspective for key policy processes and initiatives, such as the European Agenda on Migration, in order to highlight how European actors and partners can promote the integration of climate and

migration policies at the international level, through policy pathways and scenarios.

1.2. About This Report

This report is intended to highlight a number of novel scientific findings produced in the HABITABLE project for a wide audience, building from with some of the key methodological and procedural innovations of the project as well as the policy gaps identified below. As this report is not intended to be an exhaustive summary of all activities of the consortium, references to HABITABLE project outputs are provided throughout this report and in a project bibliography (Annex 1, page 37). A number of key terms and concepts are developed in the summary of novel findings (Part 2, page 20).

Habitability, in the project's working language, is defined as: "the capability of a socio-ecological system to sustain and support the lives and livelihoods of its constituent population(s)". A place should support their basic needs, provide livelihood opportunities, and foster well-being while enabling communities to thrive. It is understood as a state that changes due to internal and external dynamics and in response to changes in political and socio-economic conditions, and it includes, "a subjectivity element...as the same place can be considered as (un)inhabitable by someone but perfectly inhabitable by someone else."

This people-centred, interdisciplinary notion of habitability enables researchers to examine the "habitability" of a given *place* – enriched with human meanings – well beyond solely analysing the environmental and climate parameters of a physical space. Habitability summarises the dynamics between risk, adaptation, and place attachment that in the end affect out-migration rates – which could end up in a social tipping point² (**KO1**). Our definition of habitability focuses on place; subjective considerations as compared to objective considerations, including perceptions of affected populations – both migrant and non-migrant – regarding the habitability of local areas and the perceived benefits or maladaptations associated with human mobility³ (**KO2**); capability, understood in a human rights framing; and power, as well as intersectionality (**KO3**), within a historical and global political context

The concept of habitability holds the potential for advancing the understanding of the societal consequences of climate change, as well as for integrating systemic

² **Social tipping points** are understood as the phenomenon in which marginal changes in climate variability may trigger a discontinuity in out-migration rates leading to a reconfiguration of the social-ecological system (Gavonell et al., in prep).

³ **Human mobility** is broadly defined in the HABITABLE project working language to include different forms of migration, displacement, planned mobility (pastoralism), relocations, and *immobility*. In all four primary Sub-Saharan African case study countries, the majority of the moves recorded by HABITABLE longitudinal survey and by semi-structured interviews were internal and primarily short-distanced and likely short-term, repeated over time (Franco Gavonell et al., 2025). In Ghana, there were also long-term moves. The majority of migration reported in the qualitative interviews and FCM is toward national capital cities, while interview partners in Ghana also reported migration to other urban areas and abroad (D. A. Serraglio, de Safrá Campos, et al., 2025).

understandings and rights-based approaches into policy frameworks (KO4). See the project bibliography (§Annex 1, page 37), and particularly Sterly et al. (2025), for more comprehensive reviews of the literature on habitability and elaborations of arguments for a redefinition and reconceptualization of habitability beyond the environmental conditions focus of previous research.

1.3. Project Methods & Contributions to the Field

Study locations and partners span across West Africa (Ghana, Mali, Senegal); East/Horn of Africa (Ethiopia and Kenya); Southern Africa (South Africa), and South-East Asia (Thailand). Considerations for site selection for HABITABLE data collection included an array of climate and environmental factors, human mobility patterns, gender and social equity to speak to the project's systems-based approach.

The HABITABLE study locations are highlighted in Figure 1, with primary study sites appearing in green and secondary sites appearing in orange. More information on the survey sites is available from Gavonel et al. (Franco Gavonel et al., 2025). Summaries of contextual information for the qualitative study areas – including on community profiles, historical migration trends, and the national governance framework – are available in a series of background briefs produced as a cross-work package collaboration (D. A. Serraglio, Blocher, et al., 2025; D. A. Serraglio, de Safrá Campos, et al., 2025; D. A. Serraglio, Keeton, et al., 2025).

Figure 1: HABITABLE Study Locations. Primary study areas are highlighted green and secondary study areas in orange.

A common set of primary methods were designed and conducted across selected primary sites in order to generate comparable, harmonized, and longitudinal data and qualitative understandings, addressing weaknesses in a field largely fed by disconnected case studies. A summary of the data collection points is provided in Figure 2, encompassing:

- **Longitudinal Quantitative Surveys**, repeated across **two waves in 2022 and 2023 and including a total of 4,057 households** across Ghana (1,207 households), Ethiopia (1,024 households), Kenya (1,027 households), and Mali (979 households) (Franco Gavonel et al., 2025). The HABITABLE survey was conducted in regions exposed to climate stressors, predominantly rural populations, and communities that are part of existing migration systems. It was designed to understand changes in migration due to climate change factors by gathering detailed information about respondents' socio-economic status, household migration history, perceptions of climate shocks, and adaptive capacity to climate stressors.
- **Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping (FCM) conducted with 160 participants** in Ethiopia, Ghana, and Kenya in 2022 complements survey data by documenting populations' perceptions of an array of drivers of migration, including environmental, social, economic and political conditions, in sending and receiving areas (Reckien et al., 2025). This interview and analysis tool led to a structuring and ranking of climate change impacts and the effectiveness of (potential) adaptation measures, based on people's perception of the severity of cause-effect chains of impacts.
- **Semi-Structured Interviews (SSIs) conducted with 755 individuals across 18 origin sites and 4 destination areas** were conducted in 2022 with migrants and non-migrants in Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Mali, Thailand, and South Africa. Sites were selected from the longitudinal survey enumeration areas and interview partners were selected with local teams to best gain insight into local-level coping and adaptation strategies, as well as their interactions with migration decision making (D. Serraglio & Blocher, 2025). Qualitative information and stories were used in strategic policy recommendations as well as in developing scenario narratives for decision makers (see §1.5.2, page 17).
- **Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) across 12 origin sites** were conducted in 2022 in Ghana, Kenya, Mali, and Thailand using a participatory approach similar to Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) to explore the impacts of migration on the resilience and vulnerability of communities and groups within them, resulting in a comprehensive dataset comprising coded textual data and visualized discussion outputs (Sterly, Borderon, Sakdapolrak, Abu, et al., 2025).
- **Quantitative modelling** approaches were applied at a global scale, as well as to select contexts, to better understand and project possible future scenarios for migration and displacement trends.

**DATA COLLECTION POINTS BY METHOD
IN ETHIOPIA, KENYA, GHANA, MALI and THAILAND**

Figure 2: Data collection points by method⁴

1.4. Advancements in Practical Approaches and Gender Mainstreaming

The strength of the project's findings lies in the triangulation of diverse methods and approaches (see Box 1). Beyond the scientific advances achieved through the research methods described above, the HABITABLE project made significant improvements over previous generations of projects on the climate-migration nexus through several methodological and practical innovations. These include: (1) a more comprehensive co-development of research and policy solutions with local researchers and stakeholders, along with validation by community participants (see §1.5); (2) the use of remote and online research coordination – particularly during COVID-19 travel restrictions – through online workshops, training-of-trainers, piloting exercises, and real-time communication via messenger services, all of which enhanced North-South knowledge exchange; and (3) the systematic integration of gender and social equity considerations across all stages of research design, from objectives to dissemination, ensuring a thorough intersectional analysis.

Methodologically and conceptually, the project moves beyond traditional binary gender analyses by promoting an intersectional approach that integrates diverse social identities into qualitative and quantitative methods (**KO3**). Site selection considers not only environmental and economic factors but also social dimensions such as gender dynamics, inequality, and conflict, ensuring findings are embedded in socio-political realities (Vigil, 2021). Critical reviews of the literature (Betancourt & Zickgraf, 2024; Vigil, 2024) concluded that more nuanced understandings gender as well as of power relations across different scales are crucial for both advancing the conceptual understanding of the complex nexus between climate, migration, and inequality, and addressing the root causes of these challenges. Building on this understanding, the project views households are viewed as sites of power and negotiation rather than units of uniform decision-making, allowing for deeper insights into how gender and social roles influence migration choices. The project researchers are invited to engage in reflexivity and positionality exercises to critically assess their own biases, identities, and assumptions, thereby ensuring ethical engagement with communities and accurate representation of respondents' voices (Vigil, 2021).

Box (1): Robustness of the key findings

The key findings reported here are drawn from primary research in Africa and Asia with a research design that seeks multiple lines of evidence through diverse and complementary methods. The design involves examining a) contemporary outcomes, b) perceptions and c) governance of localities at risk from climate change impacts and currently experiencing weather-related extremes within Ghana, Mali, Ethiopia, Kenya and Thailand. It is complemented by policy analysis in these countries and regions.

The methods include:

⁴ Data summary supplied by empirical work packages; thanks to Julia M. Blocher, Marion Borderon, Ricardo Safra de Campos, Rachel Keeton, Patrick Sakdapolrak, Harald Sterly, Sarah Redicker, and Diana Reckien.

- bespoke surveys sampling affected populations on livelihood, adaptation and migration experiences and perceptions complemented by publicly available environmental and climate data;
- in-depth methods that document perceived causation, meaning and narrative from experiences of individuals in these localities;
- modelling of current risks and projected future parameters as well as co-generated future storylines; and
- policy analysis of regulatory and intervention options.

The key findings are derived from triangulation between observation, projection and causal analysis using the data and these analytical techniques.

There are complex links between climate change and migration pattern that generates uncertainties about the future, uncertainties about biophysical processes, and epistemic uncertainties around any findings. These uncertainties can be at least highlighted and partially ameliorated by the mixed method designs and investigation that promote robustness of the findings. The findings also suggest specific research priorities that require longitudinal data, greater theory building and testing from context specific cases, and policy experimentation and lessons from other arenas of policy intervention.

1.5. Co-developing Policy Solutions Fit for Purpose

1.5.1. Stakeholder Engagement

HABITABLE prioritized stakeholder engagement to ensure that research was both evidence-based and grounded in local realities. Stakeholder dialogues integrated local communities and policymakers into the research process, enabling informed decision-making and fostering the adoption of findings at different levels of governance. Through diverse methods—including policy events, community-focused dissemination (e.g., videos, graphic novels, and local events), and direct dialogues—the project helped bridge the gap between perceptions and realities, addressing misconceptions and political manipulation surrounding climate and migration policies.

Stakeholder engagement initiatives improve the dissemination and impact of research work through the following key activities:

Informing public policy through stakeholder engagement: Engaging stakeholders—ranging from policymakers to local communities—helped contextualize human mobility in a changing climate. Research findings underscored the importance of context-specific policies that consider intersecting factors such as gender, age, disability, and ethnicity. By sharing concrete insights into vulnerability and resilience, HABITABLE contributed to more nuanced and effective policy design.

Moreover, the project successfully engaged a range of stakeholders through online dialogues (despite Covid-19 travel restrictions), policy discussions, and multilingual, culturally sensitive dissemination tools like the graphic novel and scenario-building exercises. Challenges included mobilizing the right decision-makers and adapting

materials to diverse audiences, but these efforts reinforced the importance of inclusive, adaptable engagement strategies.

Community-centred dialogue and disseminating findings to affected communities:

HABITABLE emphasized the importance of listening to and involving those most affected by climate and migration challenges. Consultations with local authorities, civil society, and grassroots organizations provided crucial perspectives, ensuring that policies align with real needs and lived experiences. Beyond informing policymakers, HABITABLE prioritized making research accessible to the communities studied. Findings were shared in culturally appropriate formats, fostering dialogue and incorporating community feedback to refine conclusions and recommendations – for example, through graphic novels for four primary study countries (RIVA Illustrations, 2024c, 2024b, 2024d, 2024a). In-country community events ensured community stakeholders and decision makers were able to share, discuss, and validate the research, as seen in .

In Ghana and Kenya, the HABITABLE project stakeholder engagement included community celebrations of the research that included dance and theatre, incorporating research findings, developed and produced by the country teams and research participants. Dance, theatre, song, and photo exhibitions developed and produced by community members beautifully translated the results of the research into locally relevant engagements (see Figure 5).

Figure 3: An audience of research participants in Makueni, Kenya consider the HABITABLE graphic novel. Photos © Lucas Oyugi, DigiKollective for Samuel Hall

1.5.2. Scenario Narratives

Scenario narratives co-created with experts from Ghana, Mali, Ethiopia, Kenya and Thailand served as an additional method to aid in the co-development of scenario-specific entry points for political action and provided suggestions for adapting climate, migration and development policies to tackle the possible challenges associated with different scenarios.

Based on a bespoke conceptual model (Detges et al., 2022), which was subsequently applied in workshops to the relevant contexts, the scenarios are available in digestible formats designed to engage both expert and non-expert audiences (adelphi, 2024; Wright-O'Kelly et al., 2024). An animated video series examines how changes in the climate and environment are influencing how people perceive the “habitability” of where they live and their decisions about migration (see Box 2).

Box (2): Abdi's story

Meet Abdi, a farmer from the Oromia region in Ethiopia. After years of working the land, he is well aware that the rains are less predictable in 2030 than they used to be and has seen production from his farm suffer as a result. He and his family try a variety of strategies to adapt their farm and increase income. His elder children leave to work elsewhere and send money back, and he and his wife also diversify into other crops and selling drinks. How well they can manage will depend on many factors, including having access to education, training and healthcare, social support networks, and the amount of remittances their children can send.

[Click here to watch Abdi tell his story](#)

Figure 4: Image from "Abdi's Story," one of the videos available in the HABITABLE animated video series produced by adelphi

Drawing on insights from the HABITABLE research sites, the scenario narratives explore future challenges for agricultural and pastoralist communities impacted by climate change. They stress the need for investment in adaptation and livelihood diversification to sustain habitability, while recognizing that inequalities in gender, age, and social status shape individuals' ability to adapt (see also §2.2; page 25). The scenario narratives can therefore **support vulnerability and risk analyses informing climate adaptation planning** by presenting a range of ways in which migration and displacement can impact resilience. In each case, the scenario narratives outline policies and interventions that would protect the most vulnerable, reduce climate risks, and enhance adaptation – including migration as an adaptation strategy. They show that migration can both strengthen and reduce social capital, and that developing public goods like basic services, social safety nets, and insurance, strengthens habitability and resilience across the board – thus helping communities to withstand climate shocks and avoid displacement.

Effective adaptation planning requires local participation and co-developing scenarios with experts and affected populations ensures interventions can be better targeted.

Providing capital, education, and training supports new income opportunities, sustainable development, and resilience. Adaptation strategies should also leverage existing networks and strengthen multi-level support. Integrating human mobility into national and local plans and improving access to financing – such as remittances and climate funds – can enable self-determined migration choices.

1.5.3. Evidence for Action: HABITABLE Final Conference

A core mission of the HABITABLE Project was to expand the evidence base for tailored, informed, culturally appropriate, and gender and social equity transformative policies to address human mobility in the context of climate change. In order to achieve this, the project worked to connect researchers with practitioners and governments at multiple stages of the project in tailored language and formats.

In addition to the stakeholder engagement described above, the final conference of the project held 4-6 December 2024 in Nairobi, Kenya had multiple objectives in this regard. It aimed to discuss, triangulate, and validate key findings of the project while creating a dialogue with climate migration researchers, practitioners and experts in the field from various geographies and scholarly backgrounds. Over 120 participants from academia, government institutions, youth groups, UN agencies, and other EU-supported research initiatives discussed the next phase of a global climate mobility research agenda and built bridges to further collaborations – including, importantly, EU-Africa research partnerships. See more about the agenda in Annex 3: Concept Note & Agenda for the Final Conference.

Key take-aways from the conference included:

- The importance of evidence-based policy solutions to climate impacts in rural areas, to maintain migration as a choice and improve resilience among people on the move as well as “host” communities in origin, transit, and destination areas;
- The need for inclusive, community-led approaches to addressing climate change impacts and to giving back to the communities where research takes place;
- The importance of verification and validation exercises with local community members and decision makers;
- The need for more gendered – or best, intersectional – approaches to researching the climate-(im)mobility nexus;
- The understanding that despite generally appearing similarities in causes and consequences of migration, locality matters; differences in causes and consequences of migration across localities are larger than similarities, which means that context-specific research as well as meta-analyses remain relevant but should be better integrated;
- The necessity that local, regional, national, and international policy responses to environmental migration and displacement are cross-checked with and embedded in local realities.

Figure 5: Local girls developed and participated in theater during the community celebration in Makueni Region of Kenya. Photo © Lucas Oyugi/ DigiKollektive for Samuel Hall

Part 2: Novel Findings

This section presents novel empirical findings from the project. These findings are also summarised in a list in Annex 2 : List of Project Novel Findings, which is designed to be shared as a standalone document.

2.1. Causal Linkages Between Habitability and Migration

2.1.1. Climate conditions, perceptions, and compounding factors shape tipping points for out-migration

A key innovation of the project is to demonstrate that nonlinearity exists in the relationship between environmental conditions and migration. While much of the body of research on climate-related mobility considers migration as a response strategy to changing environmental and climatic factors, only a subset of empirical studies has explored discontinuities in that relationship.

A significant empirical finding of the project is that **climate-related social tipping points increasing out-migration rates are identified in Sub-Saharan African contexts** (related to **KO1**). The project understands social tipping points as the phenomenon in which marginal changes in climate variability may trigger a discontinuity in out-migration rates leading to a reconfiguration of the social-ecological system. Regression discontinuity analysis demonstrates the presence of social tipping points in Ghana and Ethiopia: an increase of one standard deviation in temperature anomalies leads to an increase in 5.2 and 6.3 percentage points in out-migration rates, respectively (Gavonel et al., in prep). The discontinuous jumps take place at, approximately, 0.5 Degrees Celsius (above the long-run mean) in Ghana and 0.4 Degrees Celsius in Ethiopia. The regression discontinuity analysis did not produce evidence of temperature-related tipping points in Kenya or Mali (Gavonel et al., in prep).

The difference across case study countries is likely a feature of the communities studied. In particular, analysis of the longitudinal data and **FCM confirms research suggesting that the perceptions of changing risks by those experiencing them, as much as any underlying trend, is central to the decision-making on these migration responses**. Analysis of FCM networks connecting causes and consequences of migration underscores a life-time renegotiation of migration decision-making once movement has begun, as individuals constantly (re)evaluate their circumstances, capabilities, and aspirations to return (Reckien et al., 2025). This can help account for why persons eventually choose to undertake step-wise migration, split the household across multiple locations, move from internal destinations across borders, or take other mobility-related livelihood decisions. All of these mobility types were identified in the household migration histories collected for the HABITABLE project (Franco Gavonel et al., 2025; D. Serraglio & Blocher, 2025).

The positive relationship between environmental factors and out-migration identified in Gavonel et al. (in prep), as well as the accumulation of experiences and processes of (re-)negotiation of migration decisions indicated by Reckien et al. (2025), align with a background analysis of factors driving out-migration probabilities that was conducted for

the project (Blocher et al., 2024). This research shows, through **statistical analysis, that environmental and climatic shocks have a compounding or cumulative influence on livelihoods and out-migration probabilities over time in Eastern Africa**. This study reports the probability of having a household member absent increases by 0.81% with each additional environmental shock encountered in the past 12 months, a positive relationship that holds to migration over a multi-year time window, with more recent shocks exerting the strongest impact. Different adverse events impact migration differently, with the strongest effects seen in events that immediately harm household livelihoods, such as livestock losses and crop damage. Rural, agriculturally dependent, and poor households without alternative income sources show the most significant changes in migration behaviour, likely due to the ongoing erosion of their livelihoods.

These studies add important insights into the relationship between environmental conditions and migration in Sub-Saharan Africa considering a broad time window. Moreover, they highlight the importance of looking at groups with different resources and capacities in migration research. It is likely that highly agriculturally-dependent and poor households have limited social safety nets and few options to cope *in situ*. Especially for adverse events affecting whole villages and neighbourly community-based support is therefore less available, such people may be forced to find means to cope outside their home communities.

2.1.2. Perceptions of distinct climatic factors and socio-economic vulnerabilities dictate the character and direction of mobility

Findings from the HABITABLE research using multiple methods and lines of evidence highlight several key factors influencing migration decision-making and demonstrate the importance of disaggregating data to capture the dynamics within households and communities to understand climate change and migration dynamics.

Exposure to specific types of weather-related shocks has distinct effects on whether households migrate or choose to adapt in place across study countries in East and West Africa (Novel finding). Analysis of the HABITABLE survey data (Franco Gavonel et al., 2025) demonstrates that intensification of drought periods, rising temperatures, erratic rainfall and flooding, significantly affect the frequency and patterns of human migration. When individuals **perceive droughts and floods occurring at least once a year, there is a tendency for rates of out-migration to decrease** in the study sites in Ghana and Mali (Franco Gavonel et al., 2025). The limits to migration and reduced out-migration may be explained by communities' adaptation mechanisms, and a sense of resilience built over time. Frequent exposure to extreme weather events might have led to the development of coping strategies that enable households to withstand hardships without resorting to migration. On the other hand, **perceptions of erratic rainfall and heatwaves occurring at least once a year are associated with an increase in out-migration** (Gavonel et al., in prep), a perception confirmed in qualitative narratives (D. Serraglio & Blocher, 2025) and focus groups (Sterly, Borderon, Sakdapolrak, Abu, et al., 2025). Participants across all qualitative sites reported that changes in rainfall patterns and recurrence of droughts, shifts in seasons, and increasing temperatures contribute to declining livelihoods. In Kenya and Thailand, in particular, the shift from two rainy seasons to just one is reported to be

related to out-migration by leading to reduced crop production and lower harvests, negatively impacting food security and income generation (D. A. Serraglio & Blocher, 2024). Heatwaves can have detrimental effects on human health and agricultural productivity and are reported to lead to out-migration.

Overall, participants in the qualitative interviews and focus groups reported increasing migration rates across the sites. Moreover, the **timing and character of mobility is apparently influenced by climate impacts**. For example, in focus groups in eastern Ethiopia, increases in “micro-mobility” were reported, when especially poor farmers move for short durations (e.g. three weeks) to nearby towns to get income in order to bridge periods of severe food-insecurity.

2.1.3. Economic factors take precedence as migration triggers, but climate change amplifies others within larger contexts

Across the primary data collected, economic motivations take precedence as the primary incentive for migration. Survey analysis indicates individuals and households often migrate in search of better employment opportunities and income sources to improve their livelihoods. This economic drive is followed by family considerations, such as joining relatives or ensuring better care for family members, and educational aspirations, where access to quality education becomes a significant pull factor; see Figure 6. The qualitative interviews confirmed these findings (D. A. Serraglio, de Safrá Campos, et al., 2025; D. A. Serraglio, Keeton, et al., 2025; D. A. Serraglio & Blocher, 2024), as job opportunities and extra income are the most common reasons for migration reported by interview partners from migrant households in Kenya (41) and Thailand (40). While these motivations are also mentioned by respondents in Ghana (35) and Mali (11), roughly half in Ghana noted this was to address food security. It is worth noting that food security as well as agricultural livelihoods and income in our study sites are directly affected by climate – suggesting that climate change is also a second-order driver of migration.

Direct observations of reported behaviour and perceptions from the new datasets produced in HABITABLE project (Franco Gavonel et al., 2025; Reckien et al., 2025; D. Serraglio & Blocher, 2025) show that **even if the immediate triggers are predominantly economic, in aggregate, environmental changes and shocks exacerbate other existing vulnerabilities and thus drive migration decision-making through [positive and negative] socio-economic incentives**. Figure 6 illustrates that environmental degradation indirectly influences migration through the proximate economic causes that are more commonly identified and reported by people. Individuals and households already struggling with poverty, limited access to resources, or inadequate social support systems find that these shocks intensify their hardships. The sudden loss of livelihoods, depletion of assets, or deterioration of living conditions push these vulnerable populations closer to the brink, making migration a more compelling or even necessary option. Environmental factors rank second in the FCM web of causalities when it comes to the number of causal concepts mentioned as well as the strength of causality in the migration decision (Reckien et al., 2025). This amplification effect means that environmental events act as

stress multipliers, highlighting and deepening pre-existing issues rather than serving as isolated triggers.

WHY DO PEOPLE MOVE?

Researcher involved: Sarah Redicker, Maria Franco Gavonel, Ricardo Safrá De Campos and Neil Adger (University of Exeter).
 Data provided by: University of Addis Ababa, Regional Institute for Population Studies at the University of Ghana, Samuel Hall East Africa and INSTAT Mali.

Figure 6: Primary reasons for migration reported in the HABITABLE survey

All primary data also revealed how **macroeconomic contexts, historical trends – including colonization – and local migration histories and norms for mobility matter in migration motivations.** Focus groups offered important community context, highlighting recent shifts in migration patterns across different sites depending on the availability of livelihood opportunities and labour markets. In Mali, for example, sites traditionally characterized by high international out-migration rates are now experiencing changes due to the emergence of the mining industry, which is attracting workers internally. Moreover, social and cultural norms matter; an important number (22) of qualitative interview partners in Mali reported that migration of young men is primarily motivated by quests for education, personal growth, and adventure (D. A. Serraglio, Keeton, et al., 2025). Overall, willingness to migrate in response to adverse environmental events varied across study sites, as with the highest number of qualitative interview participants indicating having migrated in response to environmental shocks in the past was in Ghana (68, compared to 60 who did not consider it), as compared to Mali (56 v. 74), Kenya (52 v. 47), and Thailand (32 v. 62) (D. A. Serraglio & Blocher, 2024).

These findings highlight the importance of understanding the specific types of environmental events and their perceived impact on communities. While some events may strengthen local resilience and reduce migration, others exacerbate vulnerabilities and encourage people to migrate. In particular, SSIs showed that the capability to

migrate is socially differentiated while FGDs indicate that shifting migration patterns - in both temporal and spatial scales - reflect changing dynamics such as the localized demand for labour, altering traditional migration flows and potentially reshaping social and economic structures within these communities. Recognizing all of these distinctions is essential for developing targeted policies and interventions that address the root causes of migration related to environmental variability (**KO4**).

2.1.4. Habitability is socially differentiated

Analysis from the SSIs and FGDs confirm our hypothesis that **habitability is not experienced uniformly across communities, rather, it is shaped by social, economic, and cultural factors that vary considerably within communities**. People with fewer resources and those with high dependence on natural resources are often more severely impacted by environmental degradation and climate change, and the latest environmental shock experienced by them pushes members of certain types of households to migrate. In particular, people self-identifying as “poor” or “very poor” were more likely to report having limited proactive coping mechanisms and experiencing declines in subjective well-being (D. A. Serraglio & Blocher, 2024). This disparity is intensified by inequalities that are often playing out across intersecting lines of difference identified in the FGDs: for example, for households or social groups situated on less favorable lands—such as flood-prone areas or drought sensitive zones—and who lack the resources to buffer losses from adverse climatic events. This differentiation manifests at a micro-level: often, the thresholds for (un-)habitability of a place vary by household, with very resource-dependent, financially marginalized households reaching limits to adaptation more quickly, prompting out-migration decisions of such households as a response to adverse events that have little impacts on better-positioned households.

Migration, regardless of its causes, appear to become a more acceptable or effective response over time as the impacts of adverse conditions or events become clearer in hindsight – or grow more severe. Analysis of the HABITABLE qualitative interviews and FGDs finds that even if individuals from migrant households do not report having used migration as an immediate response to adverse events in the past ten years, most perceive it to be an effective strategy in hindsight – regardless of the motivations for migration (D. Serraglio & Blocher, 2025). There are different explanations for why impacts of adverse conditions and events only become apparent over longer time horizons and how this relates to migration decisions, described by Blocher et al. (2024). Households require time and effort to prepare a household response, including migration. A second possibility is that exposure to adverse events may erode household resources in the immediate aftermath, delaying household adaptation and coping responses. Finally, it may be that the detrimental effects of adverse conditions may snowball or only become apparent over time. While households may perceive that they cope with a disruptive event in the short term, more substantive adjustments might be required over a longer time horizon.

2.2. In-situ Adaptation Options & Outcomes are Socially Differentiated

Using negative binomial regression analysis, HABITABLE investigates how gendered adaptive capacity influences household adaptation to climate shocks. Findings show that **the uneven distribution of adaptive capacity within households and communities notably affects households' adaptation portfolios and their decision to include migration as a response to climate shocks**. This uneven distribution of adaptive capacity is evident in behaviours and perceptions of women and men; see Figure 7, based on Redicker et al. (in prep). Women and men experience and respond to environmental stressors differently due to varying roles, responsibilities, and access to resources. For instance, women may have less access to financial assets or mobility, influencing their ability to migrate or adapt in situ. In general, women reported in qualitative interviews more past or planned adaptive strategies than men, and the latter tended to be financial in nature (D. Serraglio & Blocher, 2025). Power imbalances affect how households allocate labour and resources when facing climate-related challenges, as well as who has any say in decision-making, with implications for who migrates and who remains.

Observations of actions in the studied regions show that **migration is synergistic with adaptive capacities, underlining the capacity of migration to promote resilience in place by increasing uptake of other in-situ adaptation measures (Novel finding #7a; Redicker et al., in prep)**. This cumulative effect enhances the overall resilience of households. It highlights the potential for adaptive practices to reinforce each other, fostering a culture of innovation and preparedness within communities. Moreover, migration represents a strategic response to mitigate vulnerabilities, particularly among those with greater adaptive capacity (Redicker et al., in prep). Households possessing the necessary resources, information, and social networks are more likely to consider migration as a viable adaptation strategy. This strategic migration serves to diversify income, reduce pressure on local resources, and enhance resilience against environmental shocks. It underscores the role of adaptive capacity in enabling proactive responses to climate variability **(KO2)**.

GENDERED ADAPTIVE CAPACITY IN ETHIOPIA, GHANA, KENYA AND MALI

ETHIOPIA

GHANA

KENYA

MALI

Researchers involved: Sarah Redicker, Maria Franco Gavonel, Ricardo Safrá De Campos and Neil Adger (University of Exeter).
Data provided by: University of Addis Ababa, Regional Institute for Population Studies at the University of Ghana, Samuel Hall East Africa and INSTAT Mali.

Figure 7: Evidence on gendered adaptive capacities from the HABITABLE longitudinal survey

2.2.1. Adaptive capacities do not necessarily translate into adaptive action

Findings from HABITABLE qualitative interviews and FGDs suggest that **while some local response strategies can enhance adaptive capacities, they do not necessarily translate into proactive adaptive action for people facing intersecting vulnerabilities**. Migration, for instance, may serve as an adaptive strategy only in limited cases or for households with privileged circumstances. Across all qualitative study sites, a concerning number of interview partners reported having no preparations for future environmental events or questioned the value of such preparations. In Ghana, only around 35% of households had preparation plans, mainly focusing on adjusting farming methods, investing in water management, and saving for future shocks—while migration was rarely mentioned as a strategy for future planning (D. A. Serraglio & Blocher, 2024). Participants in youth FGDs were particularly pessimistic about their futures, with many considering leaving farming, not only due to climatic reasons but also because of broader economic and social uncertainties (Sterly, Borderon, Sakdapolrak, Abu, et al., 2025).

Many interview partners describe **responding reactively to adverse events rather than planning strategically for adaptation, often viewing migration as a by-product rather than a deliberate strategy**. However, migration's ability to offset livelihood losses is limited by low-income opportunities in common destinations and rising environmental risks. A lack of financial means—or even hope—further constrains alternative coping strategies, reducing habitability and lowering migration thresholds. Climate impacts and out-migration also weaken long-term adaptation among those who remain, limiting their capacity to plan beyond immediate survival needs. As a result, adaptation often takes the form of reactive coping through trial and error.

Overall, analysis of the HABITABLE survey and qualitative data underline migration decision-making is a complex process – negotiated and renegotiated over time – influenced by economic priorities, gender dynamics, and adaptive capacities. Economic needs drive migration, as noted above, but the ability to migrate and the choice of adaptation strategies are mediated by gender and access to resources. Strengthening adaptive capacities and promoting equitable resource distribution can empower marginalized groups, enabling more effective adaptation, whether through migration or in-situ measures **(KO4)**.

2.2.2. Complex, intergenerational, and gendered impacts of climate mobility

It is well established in migration and development literature that change exacerbates inequalities, which in turn shape migration responses, and that migration can either reinforce or reduce inequalities. The HABITABLE project advances this research **(KO3)** and identifies the conditions for which migration can improve adaptive capacities – or lead to maladaptation **(KO2)**.

Climate mobility has far-reaching intergenerational and intersectional effects, influencing equity and adaptation outcomes – weakening community resilience over time. Migration-related vulnerabilities disrupt social bonds and enculturation processes, weakening long-term resilience of the socio-ecological system (*sensu* Sterly et al., 2025;

see also Blocher & Serraglio, in prep). In Kenya and Ghana, individuals identifying as “poor” or “moderate” expressed frustration with aid structures they perceived as unfair, highlighting risks of external assistance reinforcing power imbalances and deepening tensions among land users. Households’ ability to cope with environmental shocks varied, often reflecting relative wealth. Remittance-receiving households were more likely to belong to higher wealth groups and could invest in agricultural labour and inputs, whereas poorer households primarily used remittances for basic needs and school fees. This underscores how migration can entrench local inequalities. While financial remittances facilitated adaptation—through investments in water infrastructure, modernized agriculture, and environmental conservation—social remittances from urban migrants were often described by interview partners as hardly applicable to agrarian rural settings (D. A. Serraglio & Blocher, 2024).

Perceptions of migration causes and consequences also varied significantly between sending and receiving communities participating in FCM (Reckien et al., 2025). Migrants in cities emphasized “independence,” whereas those in rural areas highlighted “family influence.” Additionally, migration’s consequences—particularly its impact on well-being—often emerged indirectly in FCM discussions as well as SSIs, revealing complex, site-specific effects of climate mobility.

Through targeted empirical research on gender and social equity, the project sheds light on how **climate stressors heighten vulnerabilities to labour exploitation and the risk of being trafficked, particularly among male heads of households, challenging conventional gendered narratives that primarily focus on women’s vulnerabilities.** In qualitative research in HABITABLE study sites, Betancourt (in prep) identifies the role of climate stressors in exacerbating existing structural vulnerabilities that contribute to these risks, with labour exploitation and modern slavery deeply embedded in economic and social inequalities (Betancourt, in prep). Government inaction in both origin and destination areas sustain exploitative migration practices. To address exploitative labour migration, HABITABLE emphasizes the need for policy reforms in both sending and receiving countries (§2.4, page 35).

Due to multiple intersecting risks, **pastoralists’ livelihoods and well-being are increasingly threatened by climate change. By 2050, as many as 30% of the total livestock in the West African region could be exposed to multiple, cumulated climate-related risks,** according to a new model (Brouillet & Sultan, 2023). When these stressors occur simultaneously or in rapid succession, they can severely impact livestock health and survival. Given the economic and subsistence importance of livestock husbandry, escalating climate pressures are likely to undermine the livelihoods of millions in the region. Moreover, consequences can be dire for the social fabric of pastoralist groups specifically, for whom mobility is part and parcel of traditional livelihoods and social structures. A study on ex-pastoralists in northern Kenya highlights that **former pastoralists who migrated to urban areas due to severe droughts often experienced poorer well-being outcomes compared to those who had already settled there** (van Duijne et al., 2024). Key challenges included loss of livestock, insecure housing, and reliance on casual labour, with many migrants reporting low subjective well-being years after their transition. This study is further supported by the narratives presented in the HABITABLE qualitative interviews, in which

agricultural challenges including livestock loss the fourth-most reported reason for reduced well-being over the past ten years (D. Serraglio & Blocher, 2025), especially in Ghana and Mali where livestock keeping is most prevalent among the study participants (D. A. Serraglio, de Safrá Campos, et al., 2025; D. A. Serraglio, Keeton, et al., 2025). These findings underscore the need for tailored livelihood support to address the vulnerabilities of migrating populations.

2.3. Cross-cutting Scientific Advancements

2.3.1. International migration patterns are likely to evolve with climate change

A HABITABLE study simulating scenarios for climate change effects on macroeconomic development and global migration shows that **under a scenario of 3°C warming, international migration flows shift by about 1% compared to a baseline scenario without climate-driven economic impacts** (Rikani et al., 2022). The study derives country-level temperature data from global climate model simulations and applies two different methods for estimating climate change effects on macroeconomic development, based on Shared Socioeconomic Pathways 3 and 5 (SSP3 and SSP5). SSP3 results in relatively slow economic growth and persistent between-country inequality, while SSP5 features strong economic growth and a simultaneous strong reduction in between-country inequality. Population and migration data are from the UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs and a recent global bilateral migration flows dataset. A global model of international migration is used, calibrated on historical bilateral flow data.

The model simulations investigate two mechanisms through which climate change impacts macroeconomic development and migration. First, destination-country income is positively related to immigration, assuming that as countries grow relatively richer or poorer, they become more or less attractive to migrants compared to other destinations. Separately, origin-country income is assumed to follow an inverse U-shaped relationship with emigration (commonly referred to as the “migration hump”). In very poor countries, economic growth is thought to increase outmigration by lifting financial constraints - in line with the idea of a “poverty trap”. In middle-income countries, people can afford the investment to move and still expect a substantial gain from doing so. Migration aspirations decline in wealthy countries as local incomes rise, however, since the expected gain from migrating may be perceived as lower.

The model simulations suggest that **climate change subtly reshapes global migration through uneven economic impacts across countries of varying wealth. Economic growth can lift financial barriers to migration in lower-income countries while reducing emigration incentives in wealthier ones. Climate change, by slowing down economic development especially in the Global South, delays countries’ transition across the hypothesized inverse U-shaped relationship.** This means countries that are relatively poor today are projected to experience high emigration rates for a longer time than without climate change. Following a scenario calibrated on current emigration rates, climate change is found to modestly increase international migration towards North America, Europe, East Asia, and the Former Soviet Union from most other world regions. All other

between-region flows decrease due to climate change. For alternative scenarios, in which countries undergo a transition along the “migration hump” based on their absolute and relative income levels, climate change has larger effects, mostly increases, on migration between and within world regions. These scenarios – referred to collectively as representing the migration transition – contrast with the scenario keeping emigration constant at historical averages. Economic constraints in origin countries are shown to be major inhibitors of global migration and drive both emigration and immigration responses to climate-driven economic impacts.

The study adds evidence that net migration figures alone are insufficient to capture the full scale of climate-driven mobility shifts, as the net effect – the difference in the total number of moves between a climate change and a no-climate change scenario – is smaller than the actual number of moves affected and masks important dynamics that shape mobility patterns. This research contributes to a growing body of evidence that climate change may have long-term effects on international migration, although most such studies focus primarily on internal displacement and within-country migration (Rikani et al., 2022).

Further extending their migration modelling approach using bilateral migration flow data, Rikani et al. (2023) demonstrate through attribution analysis that **climate change has likely inhibited global migration to date through macroeconomic effects in both high- and low-income countries**. Through a counterfactual analysis using observational data and a simple migration model, the authors show that a world without climate change would have experienced less overall global migration over the past 30 years. The historical attribution results contrast with the future projections described above – in which migration increases due to climate change – because climate change slows down the transition of poor countries along the “migration hump.” Those countries take longer to escape the poverty trap, which implies reduced migration rates at first, but once that is observed, these countries also remain longer in a high-emigration regime, and therefore experience increased migration in the longer run. Rikani et al. (2023) underlines the presence of inhibited mobility in the Global South, where economic growth has been slower. The study highlights the non-linear, indirect effects of climate change on migration, with differing impacts across richer and poorer regions. The findings suggest that climate change may continue to influence migration by delaying countries’ transitions to middle-income status, which is typically associated with higher emigration rates.

HABITABLE research finds that **climate change variably increases and hinders international migration in West Africa, based on studies using census data in Mali** (Defrance et al., 2020) **and Senegal** (Becerra-Valbuena et al., in prep) to examine how international migration responds to drought events. In Mali, analyses of population and housing censuses conducted in 1987, 1998, and 2009 indicate that **the number of droughts in the previous five years slightly increases overall international migration rates**. Specifically, one additional dry agricultural season leads to a 0.045 standard deviation increase in the international migration rate (Defrance et al., 2020). However, the effects vary by destination: migration to neighbouring countries increases more significantly, while migration to non-neighbouring African nations and France sees a smaller rise. Migration to OECD countries, on the other hand, decreases, suggesting that when

households experience a shock such as drought, they may lose the financial resources needed for long-distance migration. Women migrate internationally at much lower rates than men, but their migration also increases during droughts, particularly to neighbouring countries. Senegal exhibits some similarities with Mali, as droughts in the previous five years also reduce migration to OECD countries and increase migration to African countries (Becerra-Valbuena et al., in prep). However, in contrast to Mali, migration to neighbouring countries decreases with more dry episodes. Given the significance of these regional migration flows in Senegal, the overall effect of droughts on international migration is slightly negative.

These findings echo a HABITABLE study based on temporary internal displacements inferred from Call Detail Records, which capture the movements of millions of individuals over a three-year period (2013–2015) in Senegal (Blanchard et al., 2024). This method allows the researchers to describe the size, timing, duration, origin, and destination of internal displacements during the rainy seasons in the 2012 to 2015 period. The results show that a **poor rainy season in a given locality reduces the number of departures at harvest time – likely because people are too financially constrained to move – but increases the number of departures during the dry season.** It also makes the locality less attractive to migrants. These effects are only observed for rural-to-rural movements and are negligible for rural-to-urban movements, indicating that temporary migration from a rural area is more likely to have a rural destination when used to cope with a negative income shock. Quantitatively, a 10% decrease in rainfall is associated with a 3–6% decrease in rural migration during the harvest season and an increase of up to 15–17% during the off-season (Blanchard et al., 2024).

Also in regards to international migration, **an agent-based model for Senegalese artisanal fishers suggests that climate change neither significantly impact overall fisheries performance, due to fishers' high mobility, nor fisher's migration towards Europe.** Instead, overfishing – exacerbated by the expansion of fish meal factories, particularly in Mauritania – has led to the collapse of small pelagic fisheries since 2020 (Brochier & Puig, 2023). Social surveys indicate that extreme fish scarcity has driven many fishers to shift from fishing to migrant transport to the Canary Islands. The model further predicts that reducing fish processing capacity to 2010 levels could restore a sustainable fishery equilibrium, maintaining annual catches around 250,000 tons, even under extreme climate change scenarios. These findings challenge the assumption that climate change is the primary driver of fishery collapse and migration, highlighting the need for coordinated regional fishery management to ensure the resilience of Senegal's artisanal fisheries and mitigate broader socio-economic disruptions.

2.3.2. Dead ends and new avenues for quantitative migration modelling

Research on the climate-migration nexus suffers from numerous methodological and conceptual challenges. The HABITABLE project makes significant advancements in identifying consensus and disagreements (Beyer et al., 2023; Piguet, 2022) and, importantly, expands on global quantitative models for migration.

Methodologically, the HABITABLE project identified inadequacies of existing deterministic migration models, the dead ends and new avenues for which are succinctly reviewed by Beyer et al. (2023). In particular, the project delivered the most **robust to-date mathematical critique of widely used quantitative migration models, particularly gravity models** (Beyer et al., 2022), which are currently central to policy advice on international migration. While these models accurately describe spatial migration patterns (i.e., flows between country pairs at a given time), the research revealed they fail to capture temporal dynamics (i.e., how migration changes over time for the same country pair). This flaw arises from a key assumption—that model parameters can explain both spatial and temporal variations—which the analysis shows does not hold. The research further demonstrated that standard validation methods overlook these limitations, meaning policy advice based on gravity models may reflect statistical artefacts rather than real migration drivers. The findings suggest that gravity models, in their current form, are unreliable for predicting future migration flows and should not guide long-term policy decisions.

Other studies have contributed to making quantitative models for migration more sophisticated. A **new stochastic evolution model for country-to-country migration significantly improves on previous models in its accuracy** (Zantout & Schewe, 2024), as demonstrated by **hindcasted simulations that compare well with observed bilateral migrant stock data** in many world regions and country income groups. This is demonstrated in Figure 8, which shows global migrant stock from different origin country income groups – low, lower middle, upper middle, and high income – comparing observed migrant stock from United Nations data (orange line) to the stochastic model realizations (green line and corridors). The dark green line marks the median migrant stock from the stochastic model simulations while the darker green corridors indicate the range in which the model realizations lie (darker green marks the range in which 50% of the model realizations lie, while the light green corridor indicates the range in which 90% of the realizations lie). The model fails to predict the observed drop in migrant stock from low-income countries between 1990 and 2010, a decrease that was likely due to the impact of migration policies and unprecedented forced displacement during this period. The model also overestimates the migrant population from lower-middle income countries, many in Africa, possibly due to increasing visa restrictions enacted during this period.

MIGRANT STOCKS BY INCOME GROUPS INSIGHTS FROM THE STOCHASTIC EVOLUTION MODEL

Stochastic evolution model. A stochastic evolution model predicts migration patterns over time based on migration probabilities. These migration probabilities depend on demographics, like the size of the population back home and in the destination country, and economic conditions. For instance, large countries often have lower migration probabilities because their citizens can find enough job and educational opportunities at home. This model allows to conservatively incorporate migration data while recognizing the complexity of global migration. The outcomes of the model are typically presented in statistical terms, such as the middle value (median) and ranges of possible outcomes (percentiles).

Migrant stock for all origin income groups.

Here we find large agreement between the model and reference migrant population except for the case of low income countries. These strong differences up to 2015 are a mix of migration policies as described above and a large surge in forced displacement numbers, unprecedented in modern history, from 2010 on. Consequently, our model highlights not only the complex effects of migration policies on migration stocks but also the difficulty of future projections when migration parameters might change even more drastically.

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Researcher involved: Jacob Schewe and Karim Zantout (Potsdam Institute for Climate Research Impact - PIK)

Figure 8: Global migrant stock from different origin country income groups: insights from a stochastic evolution model. The dotted orange line indicates observed migrant stock from UN DESA reference data. The dark green line marks the median migrant stock from the different origin income groups from stochastic model simulations, the darker green corridor indicates the 25th and 75th percentile of model realizations, and the lightest green corridor show the range between the 5th and 95th percentile of model realizations (i.e. 90% confidence interval).

Another sophisticated modelling approach allows for better projections of displacement risk. Focusing on the Horn of Africa, particularly Sudan, Ethiopia and Somalia, a HABITABLE study found, through a novel probabilistic approach **considering different scenarios, climate change may cause flood-related displacement risk to increase by two to four times compared with current conditions** (Zimmermann et al., in rev.). Even higher risks are projected for some countries under pessimistic scenarios, such as a nine-fold increase for Sudan. The study integrates climatic, hydrological and hydraulic modelling. The methodology incorporates a unique vulnerability assessment, considering factors often omitted in standard risk models, such as direct impacts on houses and livelihoods, and indirect impacts on critical facilities and services. The outputs can identify hot spots and inform national and subnational disaster risk reduction measures.

2.3.3. Gender, social equity, and ethics in climate impacts: conceptual critiques and advancements

HABITABLE unique **cross-cutting approach to gender and social equity** underscores that migration is shaped by multi-scalar power dynamics, including structural inequalities at local, national, and global levels that determine who has the capacity to move or stay, under what conditions, and with what consequences (**KO3**). HABITABLE delivers an articulation of how **a feminist political ecology perspective can be applied to highlight the historical, economic, and socio-political forces shaping vulnerabilities and migration patterns** (Vigil, 2024). The project also considers global inequalities and resource flows, emphasizing how ecological unequal exchange disproportionately burdens marginalized communities, shaping migration pathways and adaptive capacities while intensifying gendered and social inequalities.

The project also challenges conventional understandings of gender in environmental mobilities research: **of 120 peer-reviewed scientific articles on the climate change-migration-gender nexus reviewed, most are women-centric and fail to move beyond the simplistic association of women with immobility, and immobility with vulnerability** (Betancourt & Zickgraf, 2024). The experiences and vulnerabilities of men, non-binary, gender fluid, and transgender individuals are often overlooked. Recognizing the importance of intersectional analysis, HABITABLE offers guidance on how to better explore gender, class, race, and other intersecting identities in research and policy (Vigil, 2021).

In **critiques of attribution science** associating individual weather events with anthropogenic climate change, the HABITABLE project produced papers **questioning epistemic and methodological conflicts** (Thorén et al., 2021) **as well as ethical and political dilemmas tied to probabilistic event attribution** (Olsson et al., 2022). Olsson et al. (2022) argue that methodological choices for extreme event attribution, particularly frequentist statistics, render climate science political and value laden and that increasing instability of socio-ecological systems is rendering extreme event attribution less relevant. Better projections of future events may be needed, for example, to developing solutions to loss and damage, for example. HABITABLE project researchers have identified, through 80 in-depth interviews with key informants, displacement itself and consequences of human mobility as forms non-economic loss and damage (Gharbaoui & Blocher, in

review). For better understandings of loss and damage to inform policies as well as the development of criteria via the UNFCCC, Olsson et al. (2022) propose that causality driven approaches are less prone to ethical predicaments than statistics driven approaches.

2.4. Identifying Weaknesses in Legal and Policy frameworks

2.4.1. Habitability must be addressed at different levels of governance

HABITABLE analysis identified a number of weakness and gaps at different levels of governance that hinder legal and policy frameworks that could address habitability and climate mobility. The project underscores the necessity of a phased legal response, addressing voluntary migration in pre-tipping point phases and prioritizing protection for forced displacement post-tipping point. Policies must align with evolving conditions to safeguard affected populations' dignity and rights (KO4).

Marchisio et al. (2024) present an interconnected framework with 30 policy options across five key areas: climate mitigation, adaptation, loss and damage, mobility, and displacement, summarised in Figure 9. It emphasizes a "social tipping point" approach to understanding climate-driven migration, guiding legal and policy responses to support affected population. This framework provides a structure for strategic legal and policy recommendations by highlighting key entry points for policy developments that can include human mobility.

Researcher involved: Gianfranco Nucera and Sergio Marchisio (Sapienza University of Rome)

Figure 9: Conceptual framework for legal and policy measures addressing tipping points.

2.4.2. Legal and policy frameworks are unspecific and inadequate

New legal analysis conducted for the HABITABLE Project of over 700 policy instruments examines legal frameworks addressing climate mobility through a human rights-based approach, which integrates international legal standards into policies affecting individuals before, during, and after migration (Ampudia et al., in prep; Marchisio et al., 2024). A human rights-based approach emphasizes protecting fundamental rights, particularly given the insufficient legal protections for climate migrants. **HABITABLE produced the most comprehensive review and analysis to-date of relevant case law, UN resolutions, and recent advisory opinions from regional rights courts and tribunals** – such as advisory opinions from the Inter-American Court of Human Rights and the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea that reinforce state obligations to support vulnerable populations.

In addition to the global analysis, an analysis of national legal and policy instruments for each primary case study country was conducted using a systematic methodology developed by the Platform on Disaster Displacement and the International Organization for Migration (IOM), which classifies each provision related to the topic in the identified instruments as either “direct” or “indirect” and “general” or “specific”. Overall, a total of **over 100 policies and legal frameworks across six HABITABLE countries** (Ethiopia, Ghana, Mali, Kenya, Thailand, and South Africa), **were analysed along with 35 instruments from regional organizations in Africa and Asia**. Echoing the global analysis, most national provisions were recently adopted and unspecific, failing to address conditions of vulnerability that may contribute to mobility drivers (D. A. Serraglio & Blocher, in prep).

2.4.3. Entry points for EU policymakers

Public media discourse in Europe often frames the relationship between climate change and migration from a Western perspective, frequently focusing on how many climate migrants may arrive at Europe’s borders. But climate change or at least the climate disturbances caused by it, have so far had a negligible impact on international migration, notably from Africa to Europe (see bespoke model results in §2.3.1, page 29). This could nevertheless change in the future, with climate change translating into either more or less international migration depending on which part of the global migration system is considered.

The HABITABLE Project developed 25 strategic recommendations – 10 for international, 5 for regional, and 10 for national cooperation – offering actionable steps for the EU to address the climate-mobility nexus, and pointing to ways to adapt these actions for other regions (Ampudia et al., in prep). These are grouped into four areas: legal actions to protect migrants, protection and assistance to ensure safety and essential services, cooperation and finance to strengthen partnerships and funding, and monitoring and evaluation to track policy effectiveness. This framework addresses both immediate and long-term needs for the EU to manage climate-induced migration across governance levels (**KO4**).

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⁵ This bibliography includes sources cited in this report as well as other identifiable HABITABLE publications. It was compiled by Julia M. Blocher on the basis of published and advanced-draft pieces of work in the project – including journal articles and other knowledge products – as of 15 May 2025. It can be viewed or downloaded here https://www.zotero.org/groups/5912260/habitable_final. To add missing references, please contact blocher@pik-potsdam.de.

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Annex 2 : Long List of Project Novel Findings

**The following were supplied by the project researchers and are presented in the order they appear in the project synthesis report.*

Novel finding: Climate-related social tipping points driving increased out-migration exist in Sub-Saharan Africa, with temperature anomalies playing a key role, according to results from regression discontinuity analysis; an increase of one standard deviation in temperature anomalies raises out-migration rates by 5.2 percentage points in Ghana and 6.3 in Ethiopia, with nonlinear jumps in migration rates occurring at approximately 0.5°C and 0.4°C above the long-term mean, respectively (Gavonel et al., in prep).

Novel finding: Perceptions of changing risks by those experiencing them are central to migration decision-making in response, as individuals continuously reassess and renegotiate their circumstances, capabilities, and aspirations once migration begins as well as over their lifetimes – and analysis of new Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping (FCM) networks identifies context-specific webs of causalities (Reckien et al., 2025).

Novel finding: Statistical analyses show that **environmental and climatic shocks have a compounding effect on livelihoods**, as they are associated with increased out-migration probabilities across multiple time periods following the shock (Blocher et al., 2024). Migration takes time to prepare, and **some households may only migrate after the impacts of adverse events become clearer** or more severe.

Novel finding: Exposure to specific weather-related shocks has varying effects on migration decisions across Sub-Saharan Africa. In Ghana and Mali, perceptions of frequent droughts and floods are linked to a decrease in out-migration, while perceptions of erratic rainfall and heatwaves occurring at least once a year are associated with an increase in out-migration (Gavonel et al., in prep).

Novel finding: Migration becomes a more acceptable or effective response over time as the impacts of adverse events become clearer or more severe, with many individuals from **migrant households perceiving it as an effective strategy in hindsight**, even if it was not a chosen immediate response to past events (D. A. Serraglio & Blocher, 2025; D. Serraglio & Blocher, 2025; Sterly et al., 2025).

Novel finding: Negative binomial regression analysis indicates that **migration is synergistic with adaptative capacities**, increasing uptake of other in-situ adaptation measures (Redicker et al., in prep). Qualitatively, **however, enhanced adaptive capacities do not necessarily translate into proactive adaptive action** for certain people who have little perceived capacity, or hope, to prepare response strategies (D. A. Serraglio & Blocher, 2025).

Novel finding: In regards to the uneven distribution of adaptive capacity within households and communities and their translation to action, newly generated quantitative and qualitative data confirm that **adaptive capacity is gendered** and

gender notably affects adaptation portfolios to respond to adverse climate conditions and events, including migration decisions (Redicker et al., in prep).

Novel finding: Targeted qualitative research in Southeast Asia reveals how **climate stressors increase vulnerabilities to labour exploitation and trafficking**, particularly among male heads of households, challenging traditional gendered narratives that primarily focus on women's vulnerabilities (Betancourt, in prep).

Novel finding: Pastoralists' livelihoods and well-being are increasingly threatened by climate change, with projections suggesting that **by 2050, up to 30% of livestock in West Africa could face multiple climate-related risks** (Brouillet & Sultan, 2023). Simultaneous climate stressors can severely impact livestock health, **undermining economic and social structures as well as the social fabric of pastoralist communities**, as migration to urban areas leads to poorer well-being outcomes for ex-pastoralists (van Duijne et al., 2024).

Novel finding: A global modelling study finds that **under a 3°C warming scenario, climate-driven economic impacts may shift international migration flows by about 1%** (Rikani et al., 2022). The study highlights that uneven economic changes across countries shape mobility patterns and, therefore, net migration figures obscure important underlying dynamics, **as climate change can simultaneously lower emigration from wealthier countries while lifting barriers to movement from poorer ones**. This research adds to growing evidence that climate change affects not only internal but also long-term international migration. Climate change has likely inhibited global migration through macroeconomic effects in both high- and low-income countries (Rikani et al., 2023).

Novel finding: Climate change affects international migration in West Africa in complex ways; census analysis indicates **droughts in Mali increase migration to neighbouring countries but decrease migration to OECD nations** due to financial constraints (Defrance et al., 2020), while in Senegal, droughts reduce migration to both neighbouring countries and OECD nations (Brouillet & Sultan, 2023). Moreover, an agent-based model for Senegalese fishers suggests that **climate change is not related to migration to Europe** and finds that overfishing that is the primary driver behind the collapse of fisheries (Brochier & Puig, 2023).

Novel finding: Widely-used quantitative migration models, particularly **gravity models, have significant disadvantages and mathematical shortcomings** (Beyer et al., 2022, 2023), but other approaches can improve certain projections, such as a **new stochastic model for country-to-country migration** that hindcasted simulations matching bilateral migrant stock data across world regions and income groups (Zantout & Schewe, 2024).

Novel finding: Novel probabilistic modelling approaches considering different scenarios can elucidate possible risk scenarios, suggesting **climate change may cause flood-related displacement risk to increase by two to four times** compared with current conditions (Zimmermann et al., in rev.).

Novel finding: Of 120 peer-reviewed scientific **articles on the climate change-migration-gender nexus** reviewed, most are women-centric and **fail to move beyond the simplistic**

association of women with immobility, and immobility with vulnerability (Betancourt & Zickgraf, 2024). More research on the climate change-migration-gender nexus is needed.

Novel finding: Most legal and policy provisions to address the climate-mobility nexus are recent, unspecific, and fail to address vulnerability conditions driving migration, according to the most comprehensive global analysis to date of 700 documents, including case law, UN resolutions, and regional advisory opinions highlighting state obligations to support vulnerable populations (Marchisio et al., 2024), complemented by an examination of over 100 national legal and policy instruments across six HABITABLE study countries and their regional frameworks (D. A. Serraglio & Blocher, in prep).

Novel finding: Co-developed scenario narratives for HABITABLE research sites in Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Mali and Thailand exploring potential futures revealed both scenario-specific entry points for political action and common themes across all scenarios – in particular, the **need for investment in adaptation and livelihood diversification** to sustain habitability in agricultural and pastoralist communities impacted by climate change, and the central importance of **public goods, such as basic services, social safety nets and insurance, in strengthening habitability and resilience across the board** (adelphi, 2024; Wright-O'Kelly et al., 2024).

Novel finding: Because new evidence demonstrates climate change has a negligible impact on international migration, notably from Africa to Europe, **25 strategic recommendations point to actionable steps for the EU** to address the climate-mobility nexus at multiple levels of governance (Ampudia et al., in prep).

Annex 3: Concept Note & Agenda for the Final Conference

The final conference of the project (4-6 December 2024, Nairobi) aimed at discussing key findings and at creating a dialogue with climate migration researchers, practitioners and experts in the field from various geographies and scholarly backgrounds.

Researches and findings on the following topics will be presented and discussed with various kinds of stakeholders:

- “habitability” as a conceptual and analytical tool;
- interactions between geo-climate factors and other drivers of migration, including social, economic, political, cultural and demographic factors;
- predictive models at different spatial and temporal scales;
- the role of perceptions of environmental and socioeconomic factors, and how these influence migration aspirations and assessments of (in)habitability;
- micro- and meso-level coping strategies and adaptation solutions;
- the impact of migration on the resilience and vulnerability of sending and receiving communities;
- the role of existing policies and legal frameworks;
- human-rights based approaches to climate migration and displacement;
- scenario narratives focusing on the impacts of climate events and migration;
- the gender and social equity dimension of the climate-migration nexus.

Conference Program

December 4

8:30 – 9:00

Registration and welcome coffee, 4th floor

9: 00 – 9:40 Introductory remarks (40 min) (Room Almasi 1, 4th floor)

9:40 – 11:00 Discussion on HABITABLE key findings (Room Almasi 1, 4th floor)

11:00 – 11:30 – Coffee break

11:30 – 12:30 Discussion on key findings (Room Almasi 1, 4th floor)

- Feedback from the External Advisory Board

12:30 – 13:30- Lunch break (2nd Floor)

13:30 – 14:30 Presentation of country specific key findings: Joint Session hosted by HABITABLE and ALBATROSS e (Room Almasi 1, 4th floor)

14:30 – 15:30 Closed-doors HABITABLE / ALBATROSS session (Room Almasi 1, 4th floor)

- Lessons learnt from HABITABLE and challenges
- How to ensure that HABITABLE findings will be integrated through

In parallel with

14:30 – 15:50 Papers presentations

50 min presentation -10 min / paper + 30 min discussion

Panel 1 – Perceptions (Room Zambezi 2, 5th floor)

Panel 2 – Environmental stressors (Room Zambesi 3, 5th floor)

15:50 – 16:20 – Coffee break (5th floor)

16:20 – 17:40 Papers presentations

50 min presentation - 10 min / paper + 30 min discussion

Panel 3 – Policies 1 (Room Zambezi 2, 5th floor)

Panel 4 – Patterns of movements (Room Zambezi 3, 5th floor)

December 5

8:30 – 11:00 Policy breakfast (led by UNESCO, **Private Session: Restricted to the HABITABLE Consortium Members and Invited Participants**) - Room Almasi 1 (4th floor)

11:00 – 11:30 Coffee break

11:30 – 12:40 Panel on community level stakeholder engagement and methodologies, sharing best practices and insights from study countries – Room Almasi 1 (4th floor)

- Habitat/Participatory mapping method (10 min)
- Community engagement in Habitable (10 min)
- Participatory project evaluations (10 min)
- Study countries background briefs (10 min)
- Discussion (30 min)

12:50 – 14:00 – Lunch break (2nd floor)

14:00 – 15:20 - Papers presentations

50 min presentation -10 min / paper + 30 min discussion

Panel 5 – Policies 2 (Room Zambezi 2, 5th floor)

Panel 6 – Adaptation and Resilience (Room Zambezi 3, 5th floor)

15:20 – 16:40 - Papers presentations

50 min presentation -10 min / paper + 30 min discussion

Panel 7 - Humanitarian situations (Room Zambezi 2, 5th floor)

Panel 8 - Gendered perspectives (Room Zambezi 3, 5th floor)

16:40 – 17:10 - Coffee Break

17:10 – 18:30 - Papers presentations

50 min presentation -10 min / paper + 30 min discussion

Panel 9 – Internal Displacements (Room Zambezi 2, 5th floor)

Panel 10 – Principles of governance (Room Zambezi 3, 5th floor)

In parallel with

17:10 – 18:30 - Habitable consortium (closed door) session (Room Almasi 1, 4th floor)

- Feedback on the project
- Next steps regarding reporting

December 6

8:30 – 9:00 - Registration

9:00 – 9:45 UNESCO side event on Equity in the Climate Transition Social and Economic Perspectives (Room Zambezi 3, 5th floor)

9:45 – 11:15 Papers presentations

50 min presentation -10 min / paper + 30 min discussion

Panel 11 – Agency and Vulnerabilities (Room Almasi 1, 4th floor)

In parallel with:

9:45 – 10:50 UNESCO Side-event - Youth Engagement in Habitability: Advocacy for Climate Resilience (Room Zambezi 3, 4th floor)

11:15 – 11:45 - Coffee break (4th floor)

11:45 – 12:45 – Conference final closing (Room Almasi 1, 4th floor)

12:30 – 13:30 – Lunch (2nd floor)

***** End of the conference*****